

POSSIBILITIES OF INNOVATIVE TEACHING METHODS IN PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7556824>

Abstract. *The article presents modern approaches to the theoretical and methodological foundations for the development of professional competence of teaching staff, clarifies the principles and leading factors, develops requirements for the content and level of professional competence of teaching staff of higher educational institutions in the context of education modernization, develops principles for increasing the professional competence of leading and teaching staff at basis of acmeological and andragogical approaches. scientific and theoretical substantiation of the improvement of organizational and managerial mechanisms of development.*

Keywords: *professional competence, pedagogical personnel, methodological basis, acmeological and andragogic approach, innovation, interactive technology, mechanism, principles, pedagogical personnel, design.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the modern trends is to ensure the quality and competitiveness of the activities of higher education institutions through the development of professional competence of personnel in the world. In the content of the concepts of "Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)" adopted at the 70th anniversary session of the UN General Assembly, as well as "European Higher Education Space" (EHEA), "the introduction of a model of competence-based learning (competence-based learning) in training and professional development of personnel, improvement of mechanisms for continuous development of professional qualifications based on humanization of This ensures the integration of foreign advanced systems for the development of professional competencies into the management and educational process.

Scientific research is underway to improve the mechanisms for the development of universal competencies of pedagogical personnel in the world education system, expand corporate education and coaching services on the basis of modern quality management principles, create intellectual information systems to increase personnel innovation activity, forecast a modern system of professional competencies based on the Forsythe methodology. The strategy of research on improving the mechanisms for the development of professional competence of senior personnel of higher educational institutions is aimed at improving the mechanisms for the development of professional competence of personnel on the basis of acmeological and competency approaches, modernizing the forms and techniques aimed at innovative activities of the development of professional competence, scientific and practical solution of.

Particular attention is paid to the issue of continuous development of professional competence of pedagogical personnel in the processes of improving the quality of higher education in our country, ensuring the integration of the personnel training system with priority

areas of development of Science and technology. In the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the tasks "to improve the quality and effectiveness of the activities of higher educational institutions on the basis of the introduction of international standards for assessing the quality of education and training, to stimulate research and innovation activities, to create effective mechanisms for the implementation of scientific and innovative achievements Modern conditions of human capital investment training, personnel training-a professional professional development project is another educational process:

- full-fledged incompatibility of the quality of human capital (motivation, knowledge, experience and abilities), professional training with the requirements of the innovative economy;

- increased demand for the development of socio-personal qualities of personnel along with professional competence in new economic conditions;

- the fact that globalization processes, along with economics and politics, cover education, culture, science, prospects for the development of education are directed not only to the unified European territory, but also to the global educational integration, which, in turn, creates the need for the development of new professional competencies in specialists, such as mobility, creativity, independent education, openness to innovation;

- the formation of modern paradigms in education, the creation of an effective technology for the formation of internal desire from the ready-made transfer of knowledge from an informed society to its assimilation, interaction of the content and methodology of professional education, training on the basis of projects, FA.

Further improvement of the quality of training in educational institutions by introducing new educational programs, modern pedagogical technologies and smart technologies into the educational process in the "strategy of innovative development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022 - 2026" the organization of Forsythe centers in leading higher educational institutions as a separate link in the system of forecasting the development of innovative activities in order to develop proposals on the scenarios of the network and regional economy, ensuring scientific and technological forecasting of the internal and external environment of the higher educational institution, development of their technological and innovative environment and priority.

This, in turn, requires the introduction of innovations in the educational system, including modern, interactive and creative methods of teaching, and the development of innovative educational programs that contribute to improving the quality of education by directing them to the industry, the modernization of the processes for the development of professional competence of pedagogical personnel of higher educational institutions. In our opinion, the modernization of education is a radical improvement of the educational system, the creation of an innovative system for diversifying educational services based on the priority tasks of socio - economic development of the country, the creation of the necessary conditions for radically re-viewing the content of training, professional development of Personnel, Training of specialists with higher education corresponding to the level

Researcher N. In his scientific research, Muslimov presupposes the implementation of the main following tasks in the modernization of higher education in content [2]:

- to create a healthy creative environment in educational institutions, to raise the quality of teaching to a new level by introducing advanced innovative, pedagogical and information technologies into the educational and educational process, to develop the skills of worldview, thinking, independent observation of students;

- identification of the abilities and talents of talented students, education, formation of a single universal system of full realization of their talent, creation of scientific foundations of individualization and differentiation of the educational process;

- optimization of the scale and volume of educational downloads by integrating related disciplines in the curriculum;

- expanding the scope of scientific research in the field of pedagogy, pedagogical diagnostics, opening a wide way to research on an individual approach to the student's personality, introducing a mechanism for their comprehensive support, etc.o.

Teacher B.Ночаев, on the other hand, in his scientific research, the modernization of tailim is the introduction of changes and innovations into all the contents of yahlith tailim touring as a social and nationwide function, toshkil the basis of the state's siesati in the field of tailim. The modernization of the Dutch state, which took into account the interest and extirerations of students, parents and the general public, commented that the Gold will be carried out [3].

Researcher, P.Lutfullaev argues in his scientific research on the ways to ensure quality and raobatedness in foreign higher education institutions, highlighting globalization as a product of non-stop change and development in higher education, and internationalization as a cytematic and supportive movement that meets the needs and requirements that exist as a result of the globalization of society, politics, economics, the labor market [4].

Competence-oriented education American linguist N.Proposed by Chomsky (1965, University of Massachusetts), the researcher distinguishes the concepts of language proficiency and competence, referring to cognition as a system of language, and competence as language as being able to use it in specific cases, and offers the concept of "competence" as a concept related to language theory, Transformational Grammar [5].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

From the empirical analysis presented above, we can conclude that professional competence is a complex set of characteristics and status of a person. It is considered to embody knowledge, skills and experience in a certain area, allowing a person to express opinions on certain issues, participate in the development of certain decisions, or make decisions on their own.

It can be seen that the two most important aspects that make up professional competence are the level of theoretical and practical training, determined by the sum of knowledge and experience that ensure the successful performance of professional tasks by the professional.

In itself, it can be seen that the development of the level of professional competence of pedagogical personnel is formed on the basis of the basic professional training they receive in a higher educational institution, in which the quality of education, orientation in the field, their interaction and continuity with the requirements of mastered professional competencies and their Real professional activity are considered.

Based on the analyzes, it was confirmed that in the processes of designing the professional competence of pedagogical personnel of higher educational institutions, it is advisable to take into account the following qualitative indicators of the effectiveness of professional activity, process-specific indicators, indicators of the development of professional communication and the personality of a mature specialist (6).

Based on these aspects, it was determined that the development of professional competence of pedagogical personnel is carried out at the following levels: axiological-motivational, conceptual, technological, reflexive and creative levels, studying the modern

requirements for professional competence of pedagogical personnel, advanced foreign experience and conditions for the development of professional competence of pedagogical personnel, as well as based on the conclusions

One of the important aspects that contribute to the development of professional competence of pedagogical personnel is the adaptability of educational content and information and methodological support.

Adaptive learning - technologies are considered to be a means of teaching that take into account the goals, interests, life experience of adult educational subjects, and at the same time give them creative approaches to the educational jargon, modular integration, adaptation to social experience, methodological flexibility arising from the level of intelligence. This technology includes:

- practical significance of educational material;
- the provision of approaches based on the integration of Science, Education and technology;
- practical learning environment;
- research-oriented education;
- problematic statement, differentiated teaching assignments, trainings, project education, etc.

One such model is "**Blended learning**" - a learning system known as mixed learning. The mixed education system is a state of harmony between the traditional education system and the distance education system. In doing so, distance education (e-learning) serves as a supporter of the traditional education system and increases its chances.

Training in the professional and personal development of the future specialist has great potential.

Training - (from English training-train-teach, train) is the main form of implementation of interactive training, which is an organizational event that allows you to master theoretical ideas and ideas that need to be studied during practical work, exercises, exchange of communication.

Another of the samarli techniques in determining the professional competence of pedagogical personnel is SWOT-analysis.

SWOT-analysis-the analysis of existing theoretical knowledge and practical experience, the solution of the problem by comparison, serves to find ways, consolidate knowledge, repeat, evaluate, form independent, critical thinking, non-standard thinking. In this case, any idea, experience, situation or process is considered in 4 directions: **strength** – strengths, **weakness** – weaknesses, **opportunitu** – opportunities, **tnreat** – like obstacles.

In the development of methodological activities in higher educational institutions of teaching, in the decision-making of the need for self – professional development of students-portfolios also have a positive power of influence.

Portfolio - (ital. portfolio-portfolio, visual.folder for documents) is one of the modern educational technologies that serve to autentic assessment of the results of educational and professional activities. The Portfolio is reflected as the sum of the sorted educational and methodological work of the future specialist or teacher, professional-personal achievements.

For educational activities in higher educational institutions: student portfolio, graduate, doctoral student, listener portfolio, etc., for pedagogical activity, it will be possible to use such types as teacher portfolio, leader employee Portfolio (7).

Summarizing the above points, it can be noted that the implementation of innovative educational technologies in the educational process of higher educational institutions is one of the important tasks facing the industry today, in which special attention should be paid to the development of normative, methodological, material and technical support of the educational process, personnel potential and skills of mastering innovations and, of course,

An effective type of innovative teaching methods in the practice of vocational education is *interactive methods*.

Interactive method-serves to activate the assimilation of knowledge, the development of personal qualities by increasing the interaction between students and the teacher in the educational process [8].

The pedagogical and psychological basis of interactive techniques was laid by the authors J.G'. Yuldashev and S.A.The usmanovs conduct research by connecting with the following theories: the theory of Constructivism (Dj.Dewey), development of child intelligence (J.Piaje), the nearest Development Area (L.S.Vigotsky), multi-species intelligence (g.Gardner) as well as the taxonomy of learning objectives (B.Blum).

In fact, the application of interactive techniques helps in the learning process to form and develop the skills of the educational institution in the cognitive and emotional sphere.

Interactive teaching is a special organizational form of development of cognitive activity, characterized by the fact that in the process of interactive learning, the educational person becomes a subject of interaction from the object of teaching, actively participates in the learning process.

Interactive teaching techniques are considered in modeling life situations, the use of role-playing games, solving problems in cooperation. Based on the conclusions of the observation carried out, it was determined that interactive teaching methods have the following capabilities in the process of developing professional competence in retraining and advanced training courses (Table 2).

Table 2

Possibilities of innovative teaching methods in the development of professional competence

Innovation teaching techniques and technology	Role in the development of professional competence	Developing goal	Type and form of application
The method "Assesment"	allows you to monitor the mastery of professional knowledge, skills and abilities, to determine the dynamics and qualimetry of the formation of professional training.	develops critical thinking, analysis and synthesis, creativity skills, cognitive activity, reflection.	it is advisable to use it in theoretical, practical and seminar classes, in the process of training, in practice.
Method "simulation or business role-playing game"	contributes to the formation of a creative approach to professional activity, decision-making of an active	cognitive activity, pedagogical improvisation, develops sociability	it is recommended in lectures, practical, seminar classes and mixed

	approach and increasing psychological training.	and gnostic abilities.	classes, in the organization of extracurricular educational work.
Method "Keys-stadi"	it forms the skills of research, creativity, mastering professional knowledge by finding solutions to abstract situations.	develops observation, fairness, correct perception of reality and creative imagination, cognitive skills.	the consolidation, control and evaluation of knowledge can be used in practical, seminar and independent education.
Technology "elpigich"	in finding solutions to problems of the opposite direction, scientific-theoretical of the topic helps students in the regulation of knowledge., helps students in knowledge regulation.	develops analytical-critical thinking, scientific cognitive activity, clarification of abstract concepts, assimilation, attention and memory.	it can be used in small groups, pairs and individually in practical, seminar and laboratory classes.
Method "Pops-formula"	it serves to increase the quality effect of mastering professional knowledge in educators, to evaluate the result of activity by freely reacting.	it can be applied in the form of work in groups in practical, seminar classes, as well as in mixed, reinforcement, assessment classes.	it can be applied in the form of work in groups in practical, seminar classes, as well as in mixed, reinforcement, assessment classes.
Technology "labyrinth"	analysis of professional knowledge of problematic issues, exercises, situations contributes to the formation of professional skills.	it is recommended for use in independent education in lectures, practical and seminar classes.	it is recommended for use in independent education in lectures, practical and seminar classes.
"Charkhpalak" technology	teaches independent thinking, self-assessment, respect for the opinion of others, strengthening professional-theoretical knowledge.	it can be used in forms of work in small groups in practical, seminar, laboratory classes.	it can be used in forms of work in small groups in practical, seminar, laboratory classes.
Method "SCORE"	teaches participants to think freely and independently, to analyze problem situations in a correct and logical connection, or to form clear	It can be used in the form of work in individual and small groups in practical classes, generalization	It can be used in the form of work in individual and small groups in practical classes,

	conclusions and attitudes towards a problem.	and control classes.	generalization and control classes.
Technology "Zinama-zina"	independent, teaches logical thinking, research, being able to influence the team, initiative, etc.	the lecture is used in the form of seminars, practical classes, work in small groups	the lecture is used in the form of seminars, practical classes, work in small groups

REZULTATY

Undoubtedly, in improving the quality of education and forming the rating of higher educational institutions in the international arena, it is necessary to develop a system for assessing the professional competence of pedagogical personnel, take into account the existing advanced foreign experience in this regard, and ensure the adaptability of these criteria to the rapidly changing conditions of the labor market.

Based on these priorities, within the framework of the research, experimental and testing work was carried out on the development of a diagnostic system for the professional competence of the head and pedagogical staff of higher educational institutions.

The purpose of the experimental test work is the development of a diagnostic system of the level of development of professional competence of pedagogical personnel of higher educational institutions in accordance with the qualification requirements in the fields of Education.

As you know, scientific research carried out in the pedagogical direction is based on its organizational and methodological foundations, the following theoretical-prognostic analysis is designed at the stage, the design stage, the study of needs, the introduction, the analysis of the process and the final results, and the qualimetric stages.

The specificity of these technological stages and their impact on the successful organization of pedagogical experimental and test work was studied, and the tasks of the activity associated with the experimental stage of research were determined as follows:

- determination of the composition of the main indicators characterizing the level of professional competence based on the classification of the content, quality of retraining and professional development of pedagogical personnel and qualification requirements for their training and competence.

- interpretation of factors affecting the processes of development of professional competence of pedagogical personnel.

- determination of indicators of the level of development of professional competence of pedagogical personnel and the selection of qualimetric mechanisms.

- analysis, generalization of the results of the assessment and the development of conclusions and proposals based on them. The effectiveness of pedagogical experience-testing work was carried out on the basis of a special program, the application of territorial selection control, the creation of appropriate conditions and the development of informative and analytical criteria that determine the level of professional competence ensured the effectiveness of this process (Table 3).

In accordance with these criteria, a diagnostic map of the level of development of professional competence of pedagogical personnel of higher educational institutions was established. This diagnostic map reflected the requirements for the level of professional competence of pedagogical personnel, which served to determine not only the reflex of diagnostic indicators, but also the

degree of effectiveness of retraining and advanced training programs. The content of the indicative structure of competencies, which allows you to determine the level of development of professional competence of pedagogical personnel of higher educational institutions, is reflected in Table 3 (9,14).

Table 3

Criteria and diagnostic map for assessing the professional competence of pedagogical personnel

Criteria	Indicators	Integrated diagnostic technologies
Information	Knowledge of regulatory legal acts of the field of pedagogical activity, social activity (K-1)	Test, essay, project work, Assessment tasks, training
	Independent search, analysis, sorting and orientation in the field of professional - activity information (K-2)	Assessment of experts based on Assessment tasks, analysis of open lessons, synergistic analysis
	The use of AK and PT in solving managerial and professional tasks (K-3)	Expert assessment based on the analysis of tests, creative tasks, open lessons, trainings
	Development of field-oriented foreign language skills (K-4)	Communicative techniques, autentic analysis
Analytical	Decision-making based on a systematic analysis of professional-managerial tasks (K-5)	Situational assignments, interviews, case analysis, decision genealogy
	Development of profile competencies, ownership of managerial skills (K-6)	Reflexive technologies, training, SWOT analysis, project work presentation, acmeogram
	Self-personal and professional development, public activity (K-7)	Naukometric and bibliometric analysis based on electronic Portfolio results, acmeogram

This diagnostic map used a level approach to determining the criteria and indicators for assessing the development of professional competence of pedagogical personnel of higher educational institutions. That is, adaptive, base on a 100-point scale in assessing the professional competence of pedagogical personnel. the productive and creative (creative) levels were determined.

To determine the reliability of the numerical indicators obtained from the experiment and the validity of the ideas put forward in the scientific study, methods of proving the effectiveness of the results obtained and its correctness and mathematical statistics were used. In order to study the practical state of the research problem and determine the direction of the necessary measures, experimental and test work was carried out in four stages. Experimental and testing work was carried out in 2021-2022, and pedagogical staff of higher educational institutions took part in it.T

In the process of experimental and test work, the level of professional competence of pedagogical personnel was assessed by means of integrated diagnostic technologies.

Figure 1. The degree of effectiveness of professional competence of pedagogical personnel

Tables were formed representing a dynamic increase in the level of professional competence in order to statistically analyze the level of development of professional competence of pedagogical personnel of higher educational institutions up to and including experimental and post-test changes. Based on the results of the qualimetric analysis, impactful indicators of the development of professional competence were determined. Impact monitoring is a system of study, assessment of the impact of the results of the development of professional competence on the effectiveness of activities. In the course of our research, the influence of the level of development of competencies on the effectiveness of professional activity was determined on the basis of Impact monitoring.

At the beginning of the experiment, according to the growth rate of pedagogical personnel, the upper level was 1.87%, while at the end of the experiment it increased by 5.87%, that is, by 4%, while at the end of the experiment the middle level was 7.58%, at the end of the experiment it increased by 14.84%, that is, by 7.25%, it can be seen that it has decreased by 18.74% (Figure 1).

These results were taxable through statistical methods. Mathematical Statistics the results obtained according to the data of the table and diagrams of the initial and final calculus in yukori through one of the methods Fisher criterion were estimated (9,10).

DISCUSSION

In the research work, the concepts of "professional competence" and "development of professional competence" as the main concepts in the process of studying the problem of the development of professional competence of pedagogical personnel of a higher educational institution were analyzed in essence and described in terms of author's interpretation. The professional competence of the head and pedagogical staff of a higher educational institution is the level of training associated with the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for effective activities in the field of Education, Management and research, personal – socially significant qualities, the ability to independently make the right decisions in clear and non-standard situations, self-control and a sense of responsibility

And the development of professional competence of educators was considered as an integrative process based on modern approaches, innovative technologies, mastering new knowledge, skills and competencies related to the industry, aimed at improving the level and quality of professional skills based on individual needs and qualification requirements. On the basis of scientific and pedagogical analyzes, it became known from us that the professional competence of the leader and pedagogical staff is classified in the following areas (Table 4).

Table 4.

Typology of professional competence

Type of competence	Contents
Competence in professional activities	Special competence arising from the requirements of the field of professional activity (good knowledge of one's work); technological competence; subjective competence; professionological competence (knowledge of the world of professions); legal competence; economic competence, etc.
Competence in professional communication	Communicative and communicative competence associated with the effective organization of pedagogical activity (ability to cooperate); socio-perceptual competence (ability to perceive other people); differential-psychological competence; diagnostic competence (ability to study others); moral competence; empathic competence; intercultural, socio-cultural, gender competence (tolerance to other cultures); competence in conflict situations, etc.
Profile (custom)	Psychological competence (the ability to learn other people) of the organization of practical activities from the point of view of the direction of activity, specialty and specialization; individual, autopsychological competence (the skill of self-study); cultural competence (acceptance of cultural norms adopted in society and assimilation as a benchmark for oneself); reflexive competence, etc.).

Also, in the course of the study, it was determined that there are the following approaches to the formation of the content and architectonics of the development of professional competence: a block-level approach, that is, a typologization of the content of professional competence in the form of base, universal, special-subject-subject competencies, which are mastered within the framework of the blocks of science.

Familiarization with the content of theoretical and practical sources has shown that the problem of the development of professional competence and competence has been studied in various directions in the scientific research of many researchers. In most pedagogical and psychological literature, professional competence is interpreted as the manifestation of professional training in practical activity, which is formed on the basis of a person's socio-professional orientation, serves to provide an effective solution to professional tasks (11). At the same time, professional competence is also noted as the correspondence of the level of professional training to the requirements of the activity and suitability. This is expressed through the requirements of the labor market for modern specialists, a complex of integrative professional and personal qualities, as well as the content of professional activities aimed at competencies.

In the process of scientific and pedagogical analysis, it was found that the problems of the formation and development of professional competence were studied in most studies on the example of training future specialists, while the structure and elements of competencies promoted in these studies were focused on the requirements of future professional activity, and the issues of development of professional competence of Taking into account these aspects, we focused on the study of the content and mechanisms for the development of professional competence of leadership and pedagogical personnel at the stage after higher education, focusing precisely on the development strategies of the higher educational institution, corporate goals.

CONCLUSIONS

Analysis of the theoretical and methodological foundations for the development of professional competence of pedagogical personnel of higher educational institutions showed that the trends of internationalization and globalization in today's educational system showed the need to improve the quality of professional education on the basis of modern approaches. In turn, the following results were achieved on the basis of systematization of andragogical, acmeological and metacognitive factors that guarantee the effectiveness of this process, as well as the interaction of acmeological criteria of professional development (professional motivation, personal-professional qualities, self-management, reflexivity, creativity) with the system of professional development and the environment of professional activity:

- organizational and managerial mechanisms for ensuring systematicity in the development of professional competence of pedagogical personnel, differentiation of educational programs based on the level of professional competence on the basis of mastering modern educational technologies and innovative approaches, introduction of alternative forms and impact monitoring systems into practice were scientifically-theoretically based on the requirements of andragogical education. Impact monitoring-a system of study, assessment of the impact of the results of the development of professional competence on the effectiveness of activities and its introduction into practice serves to increase the effectiveness of correctional and managerial processes based on a qualitative analysis of professional activity (13.15.).

- on the basis of the results of the study, keys in improving the professional competence of educators were improved on the basis of the introduction of variative information and methodological support based on innovative interactive technologies such as method, Project Education, Master Classes, reflexive training, binary training, Portfolio, creative assignments. In the process of experimental and testing work, the introduction into practice of the above-mentioned innovative methodological support has found its confirmation that it is an effective didactic mechanism for the development of professional competence of management and pedagogical personnel.

- within the framework of the study, the organizational, pedagogical and technological mechanisms for the introduction of a mixed learning (blended learning) model based on the combination of traditional and electronic learning capabilities into professional development processes were identified. The didactic requirements for the development of its comprehensive complex of resources: interactive-electronic communication based on online (LMS) and offline modes, consultative-analytical service, information-methodical support consisting of online controls and self-assessment (self Assessment) based on the time-content-result Unit have been improved.

- qualimetric mechanisms of professional competence of pedagogical personnel by clarifying the informative and analytical criteria for assessing the degree of competence, as well as its corresponding indicators, integrated diagnostic technologies (Portfolio, test tests, "assessment Center", essay, case, acmeogram and other.) on the basis of the development of the complex, it was improved and experimental-tested.

-to ensure that as a result of the research, advanced training courses are organized in accordance with the approved qualification requirements, training plans and programs; to carry out a systematic analysis of the normative-legal and didactic support of the educational process (qualification requirements, training plans and programs, assignments aimed at assessing the knowledge, skills and abilities of the audience, graduation work, attestation results); mechanisms

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